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Estimation of Crotyl and Cinnamyl Alcohols with Dichloramine-T in Partially Aqueous and Non-aqueous Media

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ORGANIC haloamines have found increasing applications as mild oxidants and analytical reagents in the estimation of compounds in solution. Dichloramine-T (N, N'-dichloro-p-toluene sulphonamide, hereinafter abbreviated as DCT) has been introduced by Jacob and Nair¹ as an oxidimetric reagent in non-aqueous and partially aqueous media and it has been used for estimating a variety of compounds such as hydroquinone², oxine³, metal oxinates³, thiols and their metal complexes^{4,5}, metal cyanides and their complexes⁶ and indigocarmine and isatin⁷. Conjugated alcohols such as crotyl alcohol and cinnamyl alcohol have a number of important applications. Crotyl alcohol finds use as a lachrymator, herbicide and soil fumigant, while cinnamyl alcohol is employed as a flavouring agent and in perfumery. In the present investigations, we have examined the behaviour of DCT towards these alcohols. While the oxidation of alcohols was found to be sluggish in 50% v/v ethanol medium, crotyl alcohol in partially aqueous medium and cinnamic alcohol solution in glacial acetic acid could be oxidized by DCT, with a two electron change. The rate was not rapid enough for a direct titration of alcohols with visual or potentiometric end point detection and hence back titration procedures were employed.

Experimental

Crotyl alcohol (Fluka, B.P. 125°, $n_D = 1.424$) was used without further purification, but the purity was checked by phthalation with phthalic anhydride in pyridine⁸. Aqueous solutions containing a definite weight of the alcohol were prepared. Cinnamyl alcohol (Naarden, corrected B.P. 256.6°) was distilled under reduced pressure and the purity

was checked⁹. Solutions of the compound in glacial acetic acid were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of the sample.

Dichloramine-T was prepared and purified by the method of Jacob and Nair¹. An approximately decinormal solution of the oxidant in glacial acetic acid (containing 10% v/v acetic anhydride) was prepared and standardized by the iodometric method¹.

Preliminary Studies :

Known volumes of alcohol solution were added to a known excess of decinormal DCT solution in an iodine flask. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature with occasional shaking, for different intervals of time. About 10 ml of 20% KI solution were then added and the liberated iodine was titrated against sodium thiosulphate solution. A blank titration was carried out with the same volume of DCT. The time required for the stoichiometric oxidation of crotyl and cinnamic alcohols by DCT was calculated. Table 1 shows the extent

TABLE 1—EXTENT OF OXIDATION OF CROTYL AND CINNAMIC ALCOHOLS WITH DICHLORAMINE-T

Time (minutes)	Equivalents of DCT consumed $\times 10^3$	Equivalents of DCT consumed / Equivalents of alcohol taken
<i>Crotyl alcohol</i>		
5	0.2951	1.77
10	0.3165	1.89
20	0.3272	1.96
30	0.3307	1.98
45	0.3343	2.00
60	0.3343	2.00
18 hrs.	0.3360	2.01
<i>Cinnamic alcohol</i>		
10	0.1840	1.11
20	0.1952	1.61
30	0.2105	1.74
45	0.2258	1.87
60	0.2325	1.93
70	0.2343	1.95
90	0.2418	2.00
120	0.2418	2.00
16 hrs.	0.2433	2.01

Crotyl alcohol taken : 0.1671 m mole.

DCT taken : 0.25 m mole.

Cinnamic alcohol taken : 0.1211 m mole.

DCT taken : 0.41 m mole.

of oxidation of the alcohols with DCT. It is seen that stoichiometric oxidation of crotyl alcohol with a two electron change takes place in about 45 minutes while cinnamic alcohol requires 90 minutes in the concentration range used.

Recommended Procedure :

An aliquot of alcohol solution (2-36 mg) was added to a known excess of DCT (~ 0.40 m mole) in an iodine flask at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ$). The reaction mixture was shaken and kept aside for 45 and 90 minutes respectively for crotyl and cinnamic

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alcohols. The unconsumed DCT was estimated by adding 10 ml of 20% KI and titrating the liberated iodine against standard sodium thiosulphate using starch as internal indicator. A blank titration was run with the same volume of DCT.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the oxidation of alcohols with DCT can be represented by equations (1) and (2).

The presence of crotyl and cinnamyl aldehydes in the reaction mixture was shown by spot tests⁹. Further, the aldehydes were isolated as their 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone¹⁰ (M.P. 189° and 253° respectively for the hydrazones of crotyl and cinnamyl aldehydes). The sulphonamide was identified by TLC technique¹¹. The solvent was a mixture of chloroform, ethanol and heptane (1 : 1 : 1 by volume) and *p*-dimethyl amino benzaldehyde in 2 N HCl was used as the spray reagent ($R_F=0.93$).

Some typical results of analyses are given in Table 2. The maximum deviation observed in

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF CROTYL AND CINNAMYL ALCOHOLS WITH DICHLORAMINE-T

Crotyl alcohol			Cinnamyl alcohol		
Compound taken mg	Compound found mg	Per cent. deviation	Compound taken mg	Compound found mg	Per cent. deviation
6.03	6.05	+0.33	2.20	2.21	+0.45
9.05	9.07	+0.22	4.50	4.53	+0.67
12.05	12.06	+0.083	6.70	6.72	+0.30
15.08	15.10	+0.13	8.90	8.93	+0.34
18.10	18.13	+0.17	11.10	11.15	+0.45
24.20	24.30	+0.41	13.40	13.45	+0.37
30.10	29.90	-0.66	17.80	17.88	+0.45
36.10	35.90	-0.55	22.30	22.40	+0.45

recovery is about 0.7%. The effect of water on the stoichiometry of oxidation of alcohols by DCT was studied. While it had little influence on the oxidation of crotyl alcohol by DCT, recoveries of cinnamyl alcohol were 3% higher when water is present above 8% in the reaction mixture. The presence of neutral compounds on the rate of oxidation of alcohols by DCT was investigated. It was seen that KCN, KCNS, NaCl (~ 0.94 m mole), KBr and KI interfere in the estimation, while Na_2HPO_4 and ZnSO_4 had no influence.

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Study of Essential Oil of *Cymbopogon nardus* var. *stracheyi*

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CYMBOPOGON nardus var. *stracheyi* (N. O. Graminae), a medicinal-aromatic species, possesses high content of the essential oil. The oil has been found to possess antibacterial and anti-fungal properties¹. Orange coloured essential oil from the fresh plant material was extracted by water-steam distillation in 0.25% yield. The physico-chemical properties determined by usual methods² were: specific gravity = 0.8924/20°, refractive index = 1.4824/20°, specific rotation = +2°/20°, acid value = 0.68, ester value = 18.75, ester value after acetylation = 98.39 and carbonyl value as $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ (oximation, potentiometry) = 8.2.

The oil (100 ml) was fractionated into its constituents employing (i) fractional distillation under reduced pressure (3-4 mm), (ii) column chromatography—using neutral alumina as adsorbent and petroleum ether, *n*-hexane, cyclohexane, benzene, ether, ethyl acetate as eluents. The purity of each fraction was ascertained by thin-layer chromatography and gas-liquid chromatography. In all ten pure fractions were obtained which were identified by preparing their characteristic derivatives and comparing their properties to those mentioned in literature³. The presence of β -pinene, 1-limonene,